

RESEARCH CULTURES IN SOUTHEAST ASIA

Characteristics, Challenges and
Change

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Executive summary

Southeast Asia - a complex and diverse group of 11 countries - has a rapidly growing research output. Research culture, which refers to the behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes and norms of research communities, influences both the quality of research produced and the experiences of researchers in different settings.

This report presents research commissioned by the Wellcome Trust to examine variations in research cultures across Southeast Asia. We found that although variations exist across the region, overall, the majority feel that research cultures are improving. However, research participants from marginalized backgrounds often do not share in the perceived improvements in research culture. They often reported barriers to career progression, less confidence in their institution's handling of bullying and harassment, concerns regarding institutional hierarchy, and that lower English proficiency limits research opportunities in the region.

Overwhelmingly, researcher participants noted the need for increased institutional support to produce high-quality research. This includes ensuring researchers have the time and resources to conduct research, greater transparency in how their performance is evaluated, better access to training and mentorship, and improved processes for ethical approval to minimize delays to research implementation.

Finally, many participants highlighted power dynamics in international research funding and partnerships. Research participants in some countries felt their research agendas were dominated by the priorities of international funders.

These findings provide unambiguous evidence of how research cultures can be both enabling and limiting. Empowering researchers across Southeast Asia requires systemic changes in institutional support, funding mechanisms, and international collaboration to foster inclusive, high-quality research environments that serve national priorities and global knowledge advancement. Recommendations to improve research cultures include:

For research institutes in Southeast Asia:

- Build inclusive research environments
- Invest in research infrastructure and support systems
- Develop transparent performance evaluation systems

For policymakers in Southeast Asia:

- Develop national research culture strategies
- Address historical and political barriers
- Invest in research workforce development

For international research funding organizations

- Prioritize local leadership and capacity building
- Address structural inequalities in funding access
- Support regional collaboration and knowledge exchange

Context and background

Southeast Asia comprises 11 countries: Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Thailand, Timor-Leste, Singapore, and Vietnam. There is great social and cultural diversity within the region, and significant economic growth and development in recent decades, contributing towards a rapidly evolving and dynamic research landscape. Research output across the region has grown dramatically between 2010-2020, with East Asia and the Pacific¹ now publishing more articles annually than Europe or North America. Table 1 captures research productivity indicators across the region.

Table 1: Socioeconomic and research productivity indicators in Southeast Asia¹

Country	Population	Income group	GDP per capita	Domestic Spending on R&D	External Spending on R&D	No. of R&D Researchers	Research Output	Quality of Institutions
Brunei	0.46	HIC	33.4	0.3	No data	514	641	3.6
Cambodia	17.4	LMIC	2.6	No data	6.4	31	10	2.9
Indonesia	281.2	UMIC	4.9	0.3	6.7	400	118	4.4
Lao PDR	7.7	LMIC	2.1	No data	1.7	No data	12	3.5
Malaysia	35.1	UMIC	11.9	1.0	0.2	726	646	5.2
Myanmar	54.1	LMIC	1.4	<0.1	1.9	19	8	2.4
Philippines	114.9	LMIC	4.0	0.3	2.7	172	27	3.7
Singapore	5.8	HIC	90.7	2.2	No data	7,225	2,150	5.7
Thailand	71.7	UMIC	7.3	1.2	1.7	1,699	195	4.0
Timor-Leste	1.4	LMIC	1.3	No data	0.1	No data	9	2.3
Vietnam	100.4	LMIC	4.7	0.4	4.4	779	84	3.5

Sources: 1) Our World in Data – Population size in millions (2023); 2) World Bank Data – Income group i.e., high, upper middle, lower middle (2024); GDP per capita in thousands (US\$) (2024). 3) Domestic spending on R&D as a percentage of GDP, including basic research, applied research, and experimental development (2022); 4) OECD Data Explorer – Official donor investment in R&D in millions (US\$) (2023), including medical research, technological R&D, and research or scientific institutions. 5) Number of R&D researchers per million people i.e., professionals engaged in conceiving or creating new knowledge, products, processes, methods, or systems (2022); Research output i.e., number of annual articles published in scientific and technical journals per million (2020). 6) Global Competitiveness Index – Quality of scientific research institutions on a scale of 1-7 (2017).

Given the evolving research landscape in Southeast Asia, it is critical to examine the developing research culture/s in the region. A recent systematic review on the culture of research revealed how multifaceted and layered this concept is.² It can involve many diverse types of stakeholders who directly or indirectly interact with research across different structures and environments, producing different understandings of research culture.

Though there are many ways to define and explore research culture, we adopted The Royal Society's (2017) definition for clarity and consistency throughout our research.³

“Research culture encompasses the behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes, and norms of our research communities. It influences researchers’ career paths and determines the way that research is conducted and communicated” – the Royal Society

Project aim and objectives

The aim of this research is to explore research cultures in Southeast Asia. The research objectives were to:

1. Understand how different research communities across Southeast Asia perceive and experience the current culture of research.
2. Identify key enablers and barriers to a positive research culture across and within countries of Southeast Asia.
3. Propose recommendations to support and strengthen research cultures across Southeast Asia.

Methods

Study design

We designed a multiphase, mixed-methods study to address our research objectives (Figure 1). Sequencing the methods allowed us to build upon findings across methods. The first phase involved a rapid scoping review to understand the current landscape of research cultures across Southeast Asia and focus group discussions (FGDs) to identify key features and issues for further exploration. Findings from the first phase informed the design of the second phase. The second phase involved an online survey to investigate the views, opinions, and experiences of different research communities across Southeast Asia, and key informant interviews (KIIs) to

² See: [Tikhonova and Raitskaya's \(2024\)](#) framework of research culture components.

³ See: [Royal Society definition of research culture](#).

gain an in-depth understanding of the enablers and barriers of research cultures across and within countries of Southeast Asia.

Figure 1: The multiphase, mixed-methods study design

Scoping review

We first conducted a rapid scoping review of peer-reviewed and grey literature. We reported the scoping review according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews. Studies were sourced from PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google. The search strategy combined terminology related to ‘research culture’ and ‘Southeast Asia.’ We developed a framework based on key components of research culture described by Tikhonova and Raitskaya⁴, and used a deductive approach to extract and synthesise data from the studies. Findings from the scoping review informed the country selection for the FGDs and the topics included in the FGD discussion guide. The full methodology and findings from the scoping review are published in a separate report.

Focus group discussions

Following the rapid scoping review, we then conducted FGDs. We conducted a total of 6 FGDs with 24 participants from Indonesia, Singapore, the Philippines, Lao PDR, and Vietnam. These countries were selected based on findings from the scoping review. We found that most studies on research culture in Southeast Asia were written by authors from Indonesia (19%), the Philippines (21%), and Vietnam (18%). A few of the studies were written by authors from Singapore (6%) and none were written by authors from Lao PDR. We represented these countries in the FGDs to capture a range of knowledge, experiences, and perspectives of research cultures.

Participants were purposively selected to balance different demographic characteristics and to represent different career stages. There were an equal number of male and female participants. Participants were mostly early-career (n=10) and mid-career researchers (n=11). Most participants were affiliated with a public academic institution (n=13). The remaining participants were affiliated with government institutions or agencies, private research

⁴ See: [Tikhonova and Raitskaya’s \(2024\)](#) framework of research culture components.

institutions, non-government organizations, or international agencies. To accommodate participants' availabilities and language preferences, the size of the FGDs ranged from 3 to 8 participants. The FGDs identified key issues to cover in the second phase of our study and helped to shape our wording of survey questions to ensure robust data collection. The full methodology and findings from the FGDs are published in a separate report.

Online survey

Informed by the scoping review and FGDs, we conducted an online survey with 646 participants. The survey comprised 11 closed questions, 1 open question, and 5 opt-in closed questions (Annex 1). The questions were designed to measure the key motivators and challenges that researchers experience at various levels – individual, interpersonal, and institutional – of the research ecosystem. The survey was translated into Vietnamese, Bahasa Indonesia, Bahasa Malaysia, Simplified Chinese, Lao, Khmer (Cambodian), Thai, and Burmese (Myanmar). We shared the survey via various online platforms and among the research team's professional networks. The survey was conducted anonymously, and the full methodology is available in the annex (Annex 1).

Despite broad dissemination, the survey received a low number of responses from Myanmar (n=8), Timor-Leste (n=4), and Brunei Darussalam(n=14). Consequently, it was decided that this data would not be included in the country-specific analysis, as the small sample sizes would not support reliable conclusions. Additionally, in some cases, respondents did not answer all questions, so results should be interpreted considering the number of responses received.

Key informant interviews

We then conducted 36 KIIs with at least two people from each country in Southeast Asia to capture underrepresented countries and research contexts in the survey. We proactively sampled from underrepresented or potentially disadvantaged groups, such as women, those of minoritized genders, and Early Career Researchers (ECRs). We used a semi-structured interview guide to understand: 1) the drivers of the research cultures identified in the survey; 2) the factors that result in differences between research environments; and 3) the main changes that researchers from diverse backgrounds feel would optimise their research. The full KII methodology is available in the annex (Annex 2).

Key findings on research cultures in Southeast Asia

In this report, we present key findings from the second phase of our study, capturing the experiences of researchers and the drivers of research cultures in Southeast Asia. The findings from phase 1, our scoping review and FGDs, are available online. We synthesised insights from a quantitative analysis of the survey data and a qualitative analysis of the KIs. Based on our synthesis, we identified three major characteristics of research cultures. First, research cultures are improving, but not for all groups. Second, researchers need more institutional support to conduct high-quality research. Third, we need to consider the role of foreign funders and international research institutes in shaping research cultures.

We also identified the key characteristics of a positive research culture. Research participants across the region consistently emphasized collaboration as the cornerstone of a positive research culture. Collaboration is viewed positively and strongly desired by participants among and within departments, organisations, countries, and regions. Team-based opportunities, such as workshops and social events that enhance relationships, were reported to facilitate collaboration and cooperation.

“A great research culture is a place where people can flourish, and ideas can thrive. It’s built on respect, honesty, and support—where people feel safe to contribute, communicate, share, be curious, and learn. It values diversity and actively encourages inclusivity” – KI respondent in Thailand

Other factors that contribute to a positive research culture include the presence of research-conducive infrastructure, resources, and support, such as sufficient time for research and supportive mentorship and leadership. Traits in individual researchers, such as curiosity, ambition, integrity and flexibility to adapt—also play a key role in fostering positive research cultures. A positive research environment was said to be characterised by values such as openness and transparency in decision-making and resource allocation, respect for academic freedom and autonomy, along with a strong emphasis on diversity, equity, and inclusion.

1. Research cultures are improving, but not for all groups

Overall, a total of 78% (n=480) of survey participants agreed their research culture was improving. In all countries analysed, between 66% and 90% of research participants shared this view (Figure 2). The KIs further explored research participant perceptions on factors improving research cultures. Research participants across the region noted an increase in the number of researchers, improvements in researchers' skills, and enhancements in the overall quality of research. Participants from Indonesia and Malaysia highlighted growth in both internal and external funding available from institutions and funding bodies. Participants also noted that more universities have shifted from a teaching focus to a research focus or have included research within their key performance indicators.

Figure 2: Agreement with research culture improving⁵

There are greater barriers to career progression among non-PhD holders, ECRs, women, those from ethnic minorities and individuals with disabilities

In all countries, most research participants agreed career progression is harder for certain groups of researchers. Across all countries, research participants felt non-PhD holders and ECRs faced the most significant career progression challenges, with 42% (n=260) of all survey respondents ranking non-PhD holders as most disadvantaged and 40% (n=245) of research participants feeling Early Career Researchers were similarly disadvantaged (Figure 3).

All participants highlighted ECRs⁶ in Myanmar are commonly rotated every 3-4 years as part of their career development. This rotation was perceived to be beneficial for promotions but challenging for ECRs to sustain their research as they had to continuously adapt to new environments and research settings. All participants in Indonesia and Malaysia shared that ECRs have little time to do research or write grant proposals due to their heavy teaching allocations and the lack of funding available to them.

Beyond ECRs and non-PhD holders, several other groups were perceived as facing significant barriers to career progression, including women (29%, n=180), individuals with disabilities (25%, n=155), and those from ethnic minorities (24%, n= 146) (Figure 3). Women (n=351) were more likely to identify themselves as disadvantaged (36%, n=126), rather than LGBTQ+ individuals (8%, n=28), while respondents identifying as “other gender”⁷ (n=17) were more likely to select themselves as disadvantaged (29%, n=5) than women (12%, n=2).

⁵ As mentioned in the Methods section, results for Timor-Leste, Brunei Darussalam and Myanmar were excluded from the survey analysis due to their low response rates.

⁶ In the survey, Early Career Researchers were grouped as students, research assistants, research support staff, research health professionals, research fellows and postdocs.

⁷ We grouped “other genders” in the survey due to the limited responses in this category. Under “Other” in the survey, we included nonbinary/third gender, prefer not to say, bayot (a Philippine term) and ผู้ชายออกสวณิดหนอย (a term in Thai meaning feminine man).

Research participants emphasized that foreigners (10%, n=63) also faced challenges in career progression. In contrast, staff at UK-funded institutions in Vietnam and Thailand felt local staff faced greater barriers to career advancement.

Figure 3: Barriers for career progression among certain types of researchers

Opinions vary on institutional policies for unethical conduct, bullying, harassment, and whistleblowing

Most research respondents felt their organizations would manage cases of unethical research conduct fairly, but there were variations in how comfortable respondents felt reporting unethical research conduct to the responsible institutional body (Figure 4). The lowest levels of comfort were reported in Malaysia (32%, n=8), followed by Indonesia (23%, n=10) and the Philippines (23%, n=12). Mid-career researchers such as lecturers (54%, n=15) or assistant professors (48%, n=13) were less confident in the institutional policies for research conduct compared to students (75%, n=23), postdocs (65%, n=44) or senior researchers (63%, n=36).

Figure 4: Organisational response to unethical research conduct and individual reporting

However, this did not always extend to confidence in institutional policies for bullying, harassment, and whistleblowing. Most research participants from Malaysia (67%, n=18) expressed a lack of confidence in their organisation’s capacity to fairly manage bullying and harassment, and whistleblowing (Figure 5). Research participants in Thailand (57%, n=40), Cambodia (59%, n=14), Lao PDR (66%, n=29), and Vietnam (82%, n=42) reported higher levels of confidence in their organizations. Female researchers were less confident (54%, n=108) than their male counterparts (65%, n=97) in how well their organisations would address bullying and harassment. Mid-career researchers such as lecturers (42%, n=12) or assistant professors (43%, n=12) were less confident than both early-career researchers, such as students (72%, n=24) and postdocs (57%, n=39) or senior researchers (69%, n=40) in how well their organisations would handle bullying and harassment.

Figure 5: Organisational response to bullying, harassment, and whistleblowing

Language proficiency shapes research opportunities in some countries

Low confidence in their English proficiency can act as a barrier to a researcher's ability to conduct research. Respondents from Singapore (66%, n=16), Malaysia (68%, n=17), and the Philippines (71%, n=36) reported a high confidence in their English proficiency. In contrast, respondents in Indonesia (43%, n=19) reported the lowest average confidence in their English proficiency and had the greatest variation in confidence among respondents, followed by Vietnam (54%, n=34) and Lao PDR (51%, n=23). During the interviews, the lack of fluency in English was reported as a barrier to getting accepted into research institutions, winning grants, publishing, or doing well in research.

"I believe that the skill of [conducting] research among the researcher in Thailand and other researcher, other professor in Southeast Asian country, we are good, but we have challenges using the [English] language, so we can't publish on research on Scopus like western countries" KII respondent in Thailand

In contrast, high proficiency in local languages can be an enabler for researchers. In Malaysia, a researcher shared some universities still prefer to teach in local languages - such as Malay - rather than English. Proficiency in local languages can also impact hiring processes; in Brunei Darussalam, locals automatically qualify for tenure.

"I think English education is important. But in local public universities, it is not the main factor for selection to become staff. They still look at the national language, Malay language. Because not all universities conduct teaching in English completely." KII respondent in Malaysia

"For the locals, they don't have to apply for tenure. They get tenure from day one of their job because they have local support. It's all about building up locals, right? For the non-locals, we expect researchers to come under the contract-based employee conditions. And so, they'll need to reapply at the end of their contract." KII respondent in Brunei Darussalam

Traditional cultural values still influence the experience of researchers from marginalized genders

Many interview participants underscored the importance of traditional cultural values in shaping research cultures in Southeast Asia, emphasizing respect for elders and hierarchy based on rank or position.

"The generation of the elderly and the Confucian approach to never questioning your elder, which is a very pervasive part of the culture in Southeast Asia. Which means [older researchers] won't get challenged, and

it's more important to be in harmony with everybody around you than to have a dialectic conversation about a topic without being threatened or threatening to others." KII respondent with experiences across the region⁸

Interview participants felt Southeast Asia had a patriarchal culture, which had mixed impacts on research participants. Participants from Myanmar felt women occupied a lower status than men in society. Men are seen in leadership positions more often and prioritized for field work, and women were perceived to prefer to stay indoors.

When navigating a research career, participants felt women were expected to consider their home life and child-rearing responsibilities. Ironically, this situation was also viewed as an opportunity for women in some instances: with men expected to be the breadwinners and often taking higher-paying jobs, which allowed women to accept the lower financial compensation that a research career typically provides.

"[In Cambodia,] I put a request forward and said, could I get her to work with us? And her boss goes, no. Everybody's out on field projects right now, so we need someone to stay home and answer the phones or stay in the office and answer the phones." KII respondent with experiences across the region

"Some female professors don't need to worry about the financial stuff because they have a husband as a breadwinner. So, in this type of female professor, they can focus on their studies and do not have to rely on academia to provide for their family." KII respondent in Myanmar

2. Research institutes' support for high quality research remains inadequate

Across Southeast Asia, many research participants noted they face multiple structural and institutional barriers that hinder their ability to conduct research. Common constraints research participants mentioned were insufficient time, inadequate compensation, limited mentorship, dissatisfaction with how organizations assess research performance, and bureaucratic hurdles, such as lengthy ethical approval processes.

Lack of time and resources are a barrier to high-quality research

Across the region, research participants reported having insufficient time to conduct research (Figure 6). This was most pronounced in Malaysia (77%, n=21) and the Philippines (55%, n=29). The main reasons for the lack of time included heavy administrative workloads related to teaching-related duties, such as grading and curriculum building, according to KII respondents.

⁸ Some of our KII respondents were classified as "regional" when they had extensive experience conducting and/or leading research in more than 3 countries in Southeast Asia.

The majority of respondents from Cambodia (64%, n=16), Lao PDR (64%, n=28), and the Philippines (53%, n=27) felt their organisation prioritised other activities, predominantly teaching, over research. ECRs (59%, n=41) and senior faculty members (52%, n=31) were more likely to report having enough time to conduct research, while only 35% of lecturers (n=10) and 36% of assistant professors (n=10) felt the same.

Researchers from UK-funded institutions (66%, n=31) and private or industry sectors (68%, n=21) were more likely to report adequate research time, compared to those in government-funded institutions (60%, n=57).

Figure 6: Researcher's opinion on their available time to conduct research

Many participants were also concerned about the lack of organizational support for conducting research. This included the absence of programmes tailored to support new academics, and limited assistance to ECRs for securing initial grants or writing publications. Participants from Lao PDR and Cambodia, especially, mentioned the absence of domestic funding as a barrier for long-term, sustainable research.

[There is] no time to do research because, you know, the duty of the healthcare workers, besides caring for patients and doing other administrative tasks, they also [have] to do research. If they are unable to produce research within three years, they will receive some punishment from management." KII respondent in Vietnam

Additionally, participants highlighted that institutional incentive structures, such as promotion criteria, did not always include research. This often led to reduced support for research activities.

"In Laotian academic institutions, while there are clear structures, promotions are still largely based on teaching rather than research. As a result, someone might remain in the same position for five years or more.

Advancing through research ranks is difficult, as there is no consistent or continuous support for research activities." KII respondent in Laos

Researchers in UK-funded institutions in Vietnam and Thailand reported greater access to resources, training and support compared to those in government-funded settings. In Vietnam, twice as many researcher participants from UK-funded institutions strongly agreed they had adequate access to resources (70%, n=16) compared to domestically funded research participants (36%, n=12). In Thailand, a similar trend was observed; 44% (n=7) of UK-funded research participants strongly agreed they had adequate access to resources compared to 19% (n=6) at domestically funded institutions.

Timelines for ethical approval hinder research implementation

Heavy bureaucracy and lengthy timelines for ethical approval were familiar challenges reported across the region. Research participants emphasised the need for funders and international partners to adapt their timelines based on local capacity for ethics reviews. KII participants emphasized the need to strengthen research ethics capacity in countries where it is strongly impacting research timelines, such as Myanmar, Timor-Leste, and Lao PDR.

In the interviews, research participants from Myanmar and Timor-Leste expressed the desire for decentralised ethics review committees in addition to the national committees to reduce operational bottlenecks.

"In most countries, institutes or university have their own research ethics review committee. But in Myanmar, the Housing Ministry of Health and Education still [has a centralized] ethics review committee, but it cannot support [the demand efficiently]. And still, they did not support the development of ethics review committees for each university." KII respondent in Myanmar

Research participants report limited access to training, funding and mentorship

Research participants commonly reported difficulties accessing programmes and funding to build their research skills. Many participants felt that international and national university rankings influenced access to funding and research opportunities. As research outputs are commonly linked to university rankings, this can lead to pressure to increase research outputs. Additionally, the ranking criteria for national or international league tables are not always equitable. For example, in Myanmar, university ranking is solely based on the year of establishment, rather than research output or impact.

"So, university ranking in Myanmar is based on the year they open. Not based on your evaluation system. They don't evaluate with research output. They don't evaluate with any human resource." KII respondent in Myanmar

Satisfaction with mentorship and support varied widely across the region and by identity characteristics (Figure 7). Research participants from Vietnam and Lao PDR were the most satisfied with the mentorship they received, with 71% (n=45 and n=32, respectively) stating they were satisfied. In contrast, those from the Philippines (47%, n=25), Singapore (38%, n=10) and Malaysia (35%, n=9) reported lower levels of satisfaction. The majority (>50%) of ECRs (n=65) and senior faculty members (n=33) were satisfied with the mentorship and support they received. In contrast, mid-career researchers such as lecturers (61%, n=17) and assistant professors (51%, n=14) reported neutral or negative experiences. Female participants reported slightly less satisfaction in their mentorship, with 56% (n=113) of women expressing satisfaction vs 59% (n=88) of men and 62% (n=5) of individuals identifying as other gender.

Figure 7: Researcher satisfaction with the level of mentorship they receive

Compensation for research activities is not always equitable

Researcher participants expressed varying levels of satisfaction regarding the compensation they receive for the time they allocate to research activities (Figure 8). Those in teaching-focused or junior roles, such as lecturers, assistant professors, research assistants, and students, generally reported lower satisfaction levels, with rates of 40% (n=11), 43% (n=12), 48% (n=22), and 48% (n=16), respectively. Participants in more senior positions were slightly more satisfied with their compensation (50%-57%). Many interview participants emphasized the importance of fair compensation for their research time, regardless of gender or nationality. They also highlighted the need for non-monetary benefits such as family support and health insurance. Interview participants highlighted that in some countries, staff are expected to do research in addition to their primary duties without receiving extra pay. This was especially common among clinician-researchers.

Figure 8: Researcher satisfaction about compensation for research time by country

Most researcher participants (77%, n=21) in Malaysia felt inadequately compensated for their research efforts. In other countries, opinions were more divided, with roughly half of the respondents satisfied, and half dissatisfied. Female participants reported feeling less satisfied with the compensation they received for research (48%, n=109) compared to men (53%, n=85) (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Researcher satisfaction with compensation for research time by gender

The lack of transparency in how organizations measure research performance negatively affects researchers

Overall respondents in the region were quite satisfied with how their organization measured research performance. Dissatisfaction with research performance assessment was stronger among research participants from the Philippines (39%, n=43), Malaysia (38%, n=17) and Singapore (34%, n=17), who showed dissatisfaction with how their organizations measured research performance (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Researcher satisfaction with how their organization assesses research performance

KII responses revealed that while most participants agreed with their organizations’ focus on using publishing in high impact journals to assess research performance, over-emphasising publications as a metric for success had negative consequences. Participants felt it undermined research integrity and increased unhealthy competitiveness in authorship among collaborators and researchers at different career stages.

Research participants also felt that a lack of transparency in the awarding of internal research grants and promotions could create a stressful environment.

"I think it is highly opaque and highly anxiety-inducing because it's like a black box. The only thing along the way that gives you any indication that you might do okay would be your mid-term review. But what if someone at the board of trustees of the university decides that 'hey, this guy's research is a little bit too politically sensitive?'" KII respondent in Singapore

KII responses revealed that over-emphasising publications as a metric for success undermined research integrity and increased unhealthy competitiveness in authorship among collaborators and researchers at different career stages. When KII participants were asked which metrics for success in research should be recognised instead, they mentioned alternative metrics such as real-world impact, good communication skills, interpersonal skills, innovativeness, integrity, and ambition.

"What is happening now is really that you focus on producing high-impact journals, and that creates a lot of violations of research ethics." KII respondent in Indonesia

3. Foreign research funders and collaborators should value local expertise more

While international partnerships and funding have brought critical resources, visibility, and opportunities for collaboration in Southeast Asian countries, participants also raised concerns about the impact of those partnerships on research autonomy. Researchers across the region, especially ECRs and those in lower-income countries, expressed concerns about the dominance of international funders and foreign researchers in determining national research priorities. These concerns stem not only from economic disparities but also from historical and political legacies that continue to affect funding flows, institutional power dynamics, and collaboration between countries.

International donor funding influences national research agendas

Most researchers from Malaysia (54%, n=24) and Indonesia (45%, n=34) felt their organization’s research priorities matched priorities for their contexts (Figure 11). In all other countries, most researchers felt that international funders and/or foreign researchers dominate the research priorities of their country. Additionally, ECRs and those in the fields of *Microbiology* and *Public health* (see annex – survey respondents) were more likely to feel that international funders and foreign researchers dominate national research priorities.

Figure 11: Researcher opinions on the influence of international research funding on national research priorities

Concern over foreign dominance of research priorities was related to the GDP per capita of countries in Southeast Asia (Spearman⁹ $r = -0.83, p=0.015$ – Figure 12). Research participants in lower-income countries were more likely to think international funders and foreign researchers dominate their country’s research priorities. Those in higher-income countries were less likely

⁹ Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient is a non-parametric measure of the strength and direction of a monotonic association between two variables, which ranges from -1 (perfect negative) to +1 (perfect positive).

to share this concern as they felt their lower reliance on international funders allowed them more flexibility in setting research priorities.

Figure 12: Researchers’ opinion on the influence of international research funding on national research priorities correlated with GDP ¹⁰

Balancing opportunities and risks in international partnerships

Collaborations with international researchers, such as via exchange programs and resulting in co-authorship, have increased according to participants from Vietnam, the Philippines, and Lao PDR. While international partnerships provide valuable resources and visibility, some KII participants felt they could also undervalue local expertise and prioritise the goals of international or higher-resourced partners.

Overall, research participants surveyed felt they were considered equal partners when working in partnership with other organizations and teams (72%, n=242). However, interviewees found it challenging to maintain their autonomy under time pressure and in situations with limited domestic funding.

“Some international researchers use their local partner to collect data and do not include them in the analysis - we call it academic imperialism. Some

¹⁰ % Agreement is the sum of somewhat agree and strongly agree. Please refer to the methods “Survey analysis” for additional information.

Western researchers will treat their local counterparts as research assistants rather than equals. That is very problematic." KII respondent in Brunei Darussalam

"Autonomy means the capacity to do the work they [research institutions] want as opposed to becoming a subcontractor for a bigger organization or consortium, and the financial freedom to walk away without having the negative consequences of walking away impact you, your life, your research, or your institution. It's difficult in an institution that relies on external donor funding because your salary is not high enough to survive. Even at the professor level it becomes an issue. You have to find that balance between teaching versus research versus chasing donor funds." KII respondent with experiences across the region

In most countries, most research participants felt equally valued compared to their western or high-income country research colleagues. However, there was a high level of variation in responses.

Importantly, in Malaysia (50%, n=13) and Singapore (48%, n=11) research participants felt less valued than their western or high-income colleagues (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Research participants feeling of equal value to Western or high-income country research colleagues by country.

In Vietnam, 46% (n=10) of UK-funded respondents felt equally valued compared to their Western or higher-income country colleagues, which is lower than the 60% (n=20) reported in the government-funded sector. UK-funded respondents in Vietnam also reported positive perceptions of institutional support for health and wellbeing (80%, n=20), time available for research (76%, n=19), and career development (70%, n=14). (Figure 14).

In Thailand, the proportion of respondents who felt equally valued was similar between UK-funded (50%, n=6) and government-funded (57%, n=17) staff. However, 80% (n=12) of UK-

funded respondents in Thailand agreed that their mental and physical health needs were supported, which is nearly double the proportion in the government-funded sector (50%, n=16).

Figure 14: Research participants feeling of equal value to Western or high-income country research colleagues by research setting

Historical and political factors may impact access to research funding and collaboration opportunities

Tensions due to historical and political factors between countries also emerged in the interviews. Inter-country relationships shaped by legacies of colonisation, war, and foreign intervention continue to influence research environments across Southeast Asia. These dynamics can cause unequal access to international funding and collaboration opportunities.

Historical relationships shaped by colonization can significantly impact access to research funding. In Vietnam, its complex ties with the United States, rooted in the Vietnam War and its aftermath, can create political sensitivities and bureaucratic hurdles for Vietnamese institutions seeking research funding or partnerships. In Cambodia, some research participants felt their research progress depended on alignment with powerful stakeholders, such as personal connections to government officials or influential funders. In Myanmar, the military regime’s control has severely restricted academic freedom, creating a stifling environment that complicates research operations and discourages individuals to speak openly.

“In Cambodia, it's very hard to do anything worthy of merit unless you are well-connected. Because only wealthy people in the country are well-connected to the government. People don't get wealthy outside of that sphere. Even if it's a democracy, the government's essentially a dictatorship.”
KII respondent with experiences across the region

Recommendations

Based on our findings, we summarise recommendation for research funders, research institutions and policymakers. Our recommendations seek to encourage greater collaboration between these stakeholders, align research priorities, and strengthen research landscapes in Southeast Asia.

Recommendations for research institutes in Southeast Asia:

Build inclusive research environments

Institutes must move beyond surface-level diversity initiatives to address structural barriers. This includes implementing policies such as comprehensive parental leave and other family-friendly policies to support caretaking responsibilities, providing language support programs, and creating mentorship networks that specifically support underrepresented groups.

Invest in research infrastructure and support systems

Institutions should restructure academic workloads to protect research time, invest in research facilities and equipment, and establish dedicated support systems for grant writing and research administration. This includes creating streamlined ethical approval processes and providing adequate administrative support.

Develop transparent performance evaluation systems

Institutions must develop clear, transparent criteria for research assessment that go beyond publication metrics to include real-world impact, collaboration quality, and community engagement. Internal evaluation mechanisms for research proposals should incorporate policy impact as a metric and require meaningful involvement of local partners.

Recommendations for policymakers in Southeast Asia:

Develop national research culture strategies

Governments must recognize research culture as a critical component of national research and development policies. This includes developing a clear set of published research priorities for their countries through wide stakeholder consultation. This can form the basis for engagement with research collaborators and foreign funders to address the country's research priorities and plans to invest in research infrastructure, supporting institutional capacity building, and creating policy frameworks that protect academic freedom while encouraging innovation.

Address historical and political barriers

Policymakers must work to address political factors that influence research opportunities and collaboration through diplomatic engagement, policy reform, and the creation enabling environments for international collaboration.

Invest in research workforce development

Countries must invest in developing their research workforce through education policy, training programs, and career development initiatives. This includes supporting PhD programs, postdoctoral opportunities, and creating career pathways that retain talent within the region.

Recommendations for international and national research funding organizations:

Prioritize local leadership and capacity building

International funders must shift from extractive partnerships to collaborative models that genuinely empower local researchers and institutions. This includes providing direct funding to local institutions, supporting infrastructure development, and ensuring that research priorities align with national development goals rather than donor interests.

Address structural inequalities in funding access

Funders should ensure funding is available to support researchers from lower-income countries and marginalized backgrounds. This includes establishing dedicated funding streams for ECR development and ensuring that funding criteria include equity and accessibility considerations.

Support regional collaboration and knowledge exchange

Rather than maintaining research collaborations primarily led by Western institutions, funders should invest in fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and joint research initiatives between research institutions in Southeast Asia.

Annex

This annex included the relevant methodologies for the key findings report. Methodologies and reports on the scoping review and FGDs are available separately.

1. Approach to the online survey

Background and objectives

The research cultures survey was designed to capture the perspectives of researchers from different career stages, disciplines, and institutional settings, with the aim of offering a broad view of the research environments in Southeast Asia.

While the primary focus of the survey was to capture quantitative insights across the diverse research settings in Southeast Asia, the results also provided contextual background that supported qualitative findings from the FGDs conducted previously. The findings from the survey identified potential areas of concern that could benefit from deeper exploration, ensuring that the subsequent KIIs were aligned with the broader patterns observed.

The primary objectives of the survey were:

1. To measure the key motivators and challenges that researchers experience across various Southeast Asian research environments.
Motivators (e.g., motivation to conduct research, enjoyment of research activities), and challenges (e.g., time constraints and compensation).
2. To assess how institutional practices, resources, and policies shape research cultures.
Institutional-level factors (e.g., ethical standards, availability of resources, policies affecting research priorities).
3. To examine the relationships among researchers within and between institutions, including support systems and collaborative practices.
Interpersonal relationships (e.g., mentorship, collaboration between researchers, recognition of contributions).
4. To identify barriers to research equity, particularly among different demographics and research levels.
Demographic barriers (e.g., career progression challenges for women, ECRs, and other underrepresented groups).

Methods

Sampling strategy

The sampling strategy involved a combination of quota and purposive sampling, ensuring smaller research communities were reached with, where possible, at least 30 researchers from each country were represented. We also committed to a minimum of 200 ECRs in our sample.

Promotion of the survey was executed on channels that would maximise responses from specific participants such as (1) career stage, ensuring a balance from early-career researchers (students and junior researchers) to mid-level and senior academics (professors, directors); (2) disciplinary diversity: STEM, social sciences, biomedicine, and humanities; and (3) geographical and institutional diversity, covering both urban and peri-urban/rural-based researchers, and different types of institutions, including government and internationally funded institutions. The survey engaged 646 researchers and academic staff across Southeast Asia.

Survey respondents – demographics

Table 2: demographic characteristics of survey respondents

Characteristic	N = 646 ⁷
Gender	
Female	365 (56.5%)
Male	263 (40.7%)
Non-binary / third gender	9 (1.4%)
Prefer not to say	9 (1.4%)
Country	
Brunei Darussalam	14 (2.2%)
Singapore	52 (8.0%)
Philippines	92 (14.2%)
Thailand	122 (18.9%)
Lao PDR	62 (9.6%)
Indonesia	77 (11.9%)
Vietnam	128 (19.8%)
Cambodia	42 (6.5%)
Malaysia	45 (7.0%)
Myanmar	8 (1.2%)
Timor-Leste	4 (0.6%)
Years of experience	
1-5 years	198 (30.7%)
5-10 years	178 (27.6%)
10-15 years	163 (25.2%)
20 years or more	107 (16.6%)
Type of institution	
Government funded	360 (55.7%)
Private and industry	181 (28.0%)
UK-funded	81 (12.5%)
Others	24 (3.7%)
Position at work	
Student	59 (9.2%)
Research assistant	86 (13.4%)
Research support staff	82 (12.8%)
Research health professional	88 (13.8%)

Characteristic	N = 646¹
Research fellow, postdoc, researcher	132 (20.6%)
Lecturer or teacher	47 (7.3%)
Assistant professor	49 (7.7%)
Senior faculty position	97 (15.2%)
Area of research (N = 832) ¹	
Biomedicine, medicine, nursing, clinical	196 (23.6%)
Microbiology, virology, parasitology	104 (12.5%)
Psychology, behavioural science	46 (5.5%)
Public health, health policy, health systems, global health	279 (33.5%)
Social sciences, humanities	136 (16.3%)
STEM (science, technology, engineering, math)	71 (8.5%)

¹Area of research received 832 responses as respondents could select multiple options

Data collection and analysis

Data collection

Data collection was conducted over a 5-week period, with follow-ups and reminders on social media platforms and emails to network to improve response rates. The online survey was completely anonymous. For ethics reasons, we did not collect any personal information from participants, including nationality. Therefore, our recruitment strategy contained social media posts, word of mouth, snowballing and referral over email. In the survey, we clarified which country participants were based in, the country they had the most experience in and how long they long participants were based in this country. This allowed us to capture perspective of locals as well as foreign researchers based in countries across Southeast Asia.

The survey was administered using the Qualtrics platform. The survey format consisted of exclusively of multiple short questions structured to elicit clear and standardised responses across various research contexts in Southeast Asia. The survey was optimised for mobile devices.

To accommodate the diverse linguistic landscape of Southeast Asia, the survey was available in multiple languages, including Bahasa (Indonesia & Malaysia), Chinese (simplified), Khmer, Burmese, Thai, and Vietnamese. After consultation with our team, we did not include Tagalog due to English being the standard for research settings in the Philippines. Each language version was tested in a pilot phase involving native speakers who reviewed the survey for clarity and accuracy.

Informed consent was obtained electronically, requiring participants to acknowledge and agree to a consent statement before accessing the survey.

Data analysis

The primary focus of data analysis was on quantitative evaluation. The analysis was conducted using R.

The first stage of analysis involved generating descriptive statistics, such as frequency distributions, means, and standard deviations. This provided an overview of key variables, including individual motivations, institutional dynamics, and demographic patterns.

Subsequent analysis employed inferential statistics to examine relationships between different variables. Statistical techniques and analysis, t-tests, and regression models were conducted to investigate variables influencing research culture, identifying correlations between demographics and experiences, and assess how institutional practices impact research dynamics.

Data was disaggregated by relevant demographic and research setting, allowing for a nuanced comparison between various groups. The analysis included segmentation of data by country, career stage, research discipline, and funding type to highlight any disparities or unique trends.

Agreement percentages were calculated by combining the proportions of respondents who selected *somewhat agree* and *strongly agree*. Similarly, disagreement percentages combine *somewhat disagree* and *strongly disagree*.

Survey questionnaire

The survey questionnaire is included in Annex 4. The questionnaire was designed in Word and was transferred to Qualtrics for the dissemination.

2. Key informant interviews methodology

Background and objectives

The survey to investigate research culture across Southeast Asia brought clear evidence of the barriers, enablers and areas for improvement to the surface. However, quantitative data collected through surveys naturally has limitations in terms of the details that participants can provide. Surveys also did not allow the research team to probe specific areas in response to participant experiences.

Therefore, KIs were conducted to deepen our understanding of the drivers of the research cultures identified in the survey, factors that result in differences between researchers' experiences in different research environments and countries and changes that researchers from diverse backgrounds feel would improve research cultures. The KIs included researchers from groups that had been under-represented in the survey.

Methodology

Sampling strategy

36 interviewees were purposive, reflecting insights from the survey. Purposive selection ensured inclusion of:

- At least three interviewees from each of the study countries
- Researchers who are underrepresented or disadvantaged, as highlighted by the scoping review and survey
- Perspectives from any sub-groups that were harder to reach for the survey

Interviewees were identified through three routes:

1. Networks from the research team
2. Recommendations from the Wellcome Trust, key informants and focus group discussion participants
3. Authors of relevant papers or reports included in the scoping review

Data collection and analysis

Following informed consent, we conducted interviews over zoom and audio-recorded with automated transcription. The research team transcribed audio files with Sonix, a subscription-based AI software. Research team members checked all AI transcriptions for accuracy and detail. Two key informant interviews were conducted in Indonesian and translated by a research assistant to capture nuance and detail that would otherwise be lost in translation.

Participants were de-identified and numbered in the transcripts. The thematic analysis involved two project team members analysing each transcript line by line, employing an interpretive approach. In this approach, the themes the researchers identified were supported by excerpts from the raw data to ensure data interpretation remains linked to the words of the participants.

3. Methodological limitations and study information

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to explore research capacity and practice across Southeast Asia, recognizing from the outset the methodological challenges inherent in conducting regional research in such a diverse and complex context. While this approach allowed for the triangulation of data sources and perspectives, we acknowledge several limitations to support an appropriate interpretation of the findings. As cross-cutting issues, aggregating data across countries may obscure important local differences, and navigating varying ethical frameworks in countries presented the research team with logistical constraints. The generalizability of our findings limited due to our sample size and composition, which cannot fully account for the differences in such a geographically vast and diverse region.

For our online survey, there was risk of non-representative sampling, given the lower response rates in smaller countries such as Myanmar (8 responses) and Timor-Leste (4 responses). The survey was completely anonymous as a requirement of our ethical approval, which increases the risk that the respondents may not be representative of the broader population. There is also an anonymity trade-off; no follow-up or clarification of responses was possible for our open-ended question in the survey.

Some of the sample for our online survey may also be less likely to participate due to political sensitivity; a Burmese researcher shared that, due to the ongoing political crisis in Myanmar, many academics have migrated overseas, while those remaining in the country may be hesitant to participate out of fear of prosecution. A small percentage of the answers were incomplete or inaccurate. The survey contained a technical translation error for one of the questions on career progression, which led to an adjustment of the interpretation of this question for the results.

In terms of research settings, most research participants in our sample worked for universities, with a lower representation of researchers working in the private and government sectors. Despite wide dissemination, there was limited representation of minoritized and disadvantaged groups in the survey. KII participants were purposively selected to ensure representation of these groups in the research.

For the KIIs, the research team used purposive sampling to reach disadvantaged groups, but this did increase the risk of bias. Remote qualitative data collection may have affected openness and rapport building between the interviewer and the participant. Translating across multiple languages for the survey and KIIs may mean some nuance or meaning may have been lost during translation.

Generative AI statement

We acknowledge the limited use of AI tools for the completion of this report. The research team used Chat GPT to correct grammar and improve wording of survey questions. We used Sonix, an automatic transcription software to transcribe audio files from focus group discussions and key informant interviews.

Ethical approval

This study received ethical approvals from the Indonesian National Scientific Psychology Consortium (Konsorsium Psikologi Ilmiah Nusantara number 206/2024 Etik/KPIN) and the National University of Singapore with the following titles: “NUS-IRB-2024-858: Exploring Research Cultures in Southeast Asia through Focus Group Discussions”, and “NUS-IRB-2025-224: Exploring Research Cultures in Southeast Asia through Key Informant Interviews.”

4. Survey questionnaire

Introduction page

Gaining a deeper understanding of the Research Cultures in Southeast Asia

Research Culture is behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes, and norms of our research communities. It influences researchers' career paths and determines the way that research is conducted and communicated (The Royal Society of Science, 2018).

Please contribute to improving our understanding of research cultures in Southeast Asia, their impacts, what makes a great research culture, and the changes needed to improve such cultures.

This survey can be completed in 3 minutes. If you select to provide additional information, it may take approximately 10 minutes.

This important work is funded through the Wellcome Trust and led by The Equity Collective, a team of researchers and practitioners based in Southeast Asia and the United Kingdom.

Your insights are invaluable in shaping positive transformations for research cultures across the region.

Consent:

By proceeding, you agree to participate in this study voluntarily. Your responses will remain confidential and will only be used for research purposes. You are free to withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Thank you for your time and contribution to this important work!

Questionnaire

About you	Response
<i>These questions should take 2-3 mins to complete</i>	
1. Gender: How do you identify	<input type="checkbox"/> Man <input type="checkbox"/> Non-binary/third gender <input type="checkbox"/> Woman <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer to self-describe (please specify)
2. Which country are you currently based in?	<input type="checkbox"/> Brunei Darussalam <input type="checkbox"/> Cambodia <input type="checkbox"/> Indonesia <input type="checkbox"/> Lao PDR <input type="checkbox"/> Malaysia <input type="checkbox"/> Myanmar <input type="checkbox"/> Singapore <input type="checkbox"/> Philippines <input type="checkbox"/> Timor-Leste <input type="checkbox"/> Thailand <input type="checkbox"/> Vietnam <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
3. Which is the main country that you have had experience working in? <i>Please answer all questions that follow referring to the country you selected. If you have experience in more than one country, please complete a separate survey for each.</i> <i>By having experience working in, you have either:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Physically working in the country, or</i> • <i>Being employed by institutions based in the country, or</i> • <i>Working on projects that involve interaction with the country's citizens or officials</i> 	<input type="checkbox"/> Brunei Darussalam <input type="checkbox"/> Cambodia <input type="checkbox"/> Indonesia <input type="checkbox"/> Lao PDR <input type="checkbox"/> Malaysia <input type="checkbox"/> Myanmar <input type="checkbox"/> Singapore <input type="checkbox"/> Philippines <input type="checkbox"/> Timor-Leste <input type="checkbox"/> Thailand <input type="checkbox"/> Vietnam <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)

4. How many years have you worked in this country? (Range: 1-50)	Please enter a number.
5. What type of organization do you work at in this country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Research Institution or Centre (government-funded) <input type="checkbox"/> Private Research Institution or Centre <input type="checkbox"/> Public University (government-funded) <input type="checkbox"/> Private University <input type="checkbox"/> Public Hospital or Health-related Facility (government-funded) <input type="checkbox"/> Private Hospital or Health-related Facility <input type="checkbox"/> Externally funded Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Industry or Business <input type="checkbox"/> Funder or Philanthropic Organization <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
6. Is this organization funded through and run in partnership with UK institutions, such as the Wellcome-funded institutions: Oxford University Clinical Research Unit (OUCRU), Mahidol Oxford tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7. Which of the following best describes your main position at work in this organization? <i>Please pick one role that best describes your main job.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Student (BSc, BA, MSc, MA, MPH, MD, PhD) <input type="checkbox"/> Research assistant <input type="checkbox"/> Research fellow, post-doctoral fellow, or other research positions <input type="checkbox"/> Assistant Professor <input type="checkbox"/> Associate Professor <input type="checkbox"/> Full Professor <input type="checkbox"/> Lecturer (main job is teaching, no research) <input type="checkbox"/> Dean or head of department <input type="checkbox"/> Research administrator or manager <input type="checkbox"/> Lab technician <input type="checkbox"/> Research doctor or nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
8. How would you describe your main area(s) of research?	<input type="checkbox"/> Biomedicine, medicine, nursing, clinical <input type="checkbox"/> Microbiology, virology, parasitology <input type="checkbox"/> STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Maths)

	<input type="checkbox"/> Public health, health policy, health systems, global health <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology, behavioural science <input type="checkbox"/> Social sciences, humanities <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
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Your experience of research culture

(You can end the survey after answering 6 questions here).

Please note that all the following questions refer to the country and organization you selected.

	Big Picture Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know how to answer
Overall	1. I think research culture is evolving for the better.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	2. There is equity in decision-making and giving credit for research within my organisation.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Power	3. International research funders and/or foreign researchers dominate the research priorities of my country.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	4. I am satisfied with the way research performance is assessed in my organization e.g., academic publications, or obtaining a research grant.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
R'ships amongst	5. At my organization, there is collaboration rather than competition between researchers.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Identity	6. Career progression (e.g., to senior positions) is harder for the following types of researchers: (multiple choice)	<input type="checkbox"/> Women <input type="checkbox"/> Ethnic minorities <input type="checkbox"/> People living with disabilities <input type="checkbox"/> Early career researchers <input type="checkbox"/> LGBTQ+ <input type="checkbox"/> Foreigners <input type="checkbox"/> Non-PhD holders <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
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It would be very helpful if you could provide more detailed on your experiences of research culture. Do you have 6-10 more minutes?

- If NO, you will be asked to describe what a great research culture would mean for you, share concerns about your research environment, or suggest improvements. This will complete the survey.
- If YES, you will proceed to some additional questions. The survey will finish after this.

Individual level questions

Notes	Research Cultures Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know how to answer
Motivators	1. There is a sense at my organization that researchers enjoy their research activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Values & Behaviours	2. At my organization, researchers are held to high standards of ethical research practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Values & Behaviours	3. I feel inferior to Western or high-income country researchers.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Autonomy	4. At my organization, I am given the freedom to pursue research projects that align with my interests.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Knowledge-do gap	5. I feel confident that I have the necessary knowledge, skills and experience to conduct research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Mental health	6. At my organization, individual needs for mental or physical health support are well addressed.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Knowledge-do gap	7. My proficiency level in the English language does not affect my experience in conducting research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Knowledge-do gap	8. At my organization, I feel that I am well-compensated for the time that I allocate for research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Knowledge-do gap	9. I have enough time in my day-to-day schedule to conduct research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Interpersonal level questions

Notes	Research Cultures Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know how to answer
R'ships amongst	10. At my organization, there are sometimes tensions between researchers from different departments, disciplines or countries.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
R'ships amongst	11. At my organization, my contribution is fairly recognized (by my seniors) in research outputs such as papers and conference presentations.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
R'ships between	12. I feel that my supervisors are supportive by valuing my contributions to research and encouraging me to prioritize research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
R'ships between	13. I am satisfied with the level of research mentorship I currently receive.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Institutional level questions

Notes	Research Cultures Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know how to answer
Account-ability	14. If I witness inappropriate research or professional conduct in my organization, I am aware of effective systems to report this internally.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Account-ability	15. I am confident that my organization can deal with cases of unethical research conduct fairly.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Account-ability	16. I am confident that my organization can deal with bullying, harassment, including whistleblowing fairly.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	17. At my organization, there are systems and resources to support conducting research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	18. My organization prioritizes other activities, such as teaching, over research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	19. I agree with the level of importance given to publications in high-quality academic journals by my organization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	20. At my organization, there are opportunities for professional development and growth in research.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Policies, practice	21. The research funding my organization receives reflects key priorities in my country/context.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Resources	22. There are sufficient resources to conduct quality research at my organization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Resources	23. My organization has specific programs to help new academics get their research	<input type="checkbox"/>					

	started and to learn academic skills such as academic writing, literature review, data analysis.						
Resources	24. My organization has initiatives to support new or junior researchers to get initial grants or publications.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Pressure	25. I find it a challenge to keep up with the research expectations of my organization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Inter-institutional level questions

Notes	Research Cultures Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know how to answer
R'ships between	26. I have had an overall positive experience collaborating on research projects with other institutions in Southeast Asia.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
R'ships between	27. I have had an overall positive experience collaborating on research projects with other institutions beyond Southeast Asia.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Power	28. In collaboration work, I feel that my organization and my team are considered equal partners to other organizations and teams.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Power	29. In collaborative work, my organization is fairly recognized in research outputs such as papers and conference presentations.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Closing

N/A	Please describe what a great research culture would mean for you and please use this space to share any concerns about your research environment or suggestions for positive changes that have not already been covered.	Free text
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